

Supplementary File 1 - Serum and saliva immunoglobulins (IgG, IgA and IgM) dynamics in newborn calves and their association with health status during the first week of life: An exploratory study. By Silva et al. (2025)

Supplementary Table 1. Scoring system for the newborn ethophysiological profile evaluation, being 0 the ideal state and 3 the worst state. Adapted from Schulz et al. (1997); Mee (2008); Murray (2014).

Variable	Score			
	0	1	2	3
Meconium staining	No staining	Around the perianal area	Across the body	Hair coat completely covered
Head/tongue swelling	Normal	Tongue protruding out of the mouth	Swollen tongue protruding out of the mouth	Head and tongue swollen
Stimulus response ¹	Shakes head vigorously	Moves head away	Twitches	Does not respond
Suckling reflex	Strong	Weak		Absent
Independent locomotion ²	< 1 h	1 – 2 h	> 2 h	Cannot stand alone
Rectal temperature (°C) ³	Normal: 39.0-39.5	Abnormal: 39.6-40.0	-	-

¹ A piece of straw as introduced in one of the nostrils and the response was evaluated; ² Achieved when the calf was able to stand and move on its own; ³ ≤ 1 h after birth.

Supplementary Table 2. Scoring chart for the assessment of the calf's health status.

Variable	Score			
	0	1	2	3
Attitude	Lively, alert, and responsive	Apathetic, depressed, less responsive	Apathetic, very depressed, very unresponsive	Does not respond to any stimulus
Activity	Stands up without help, active	Stands up slowly without help, less active	Needs help to stand, inactive	Unable to stand without help
Ears	Upright, alert, active	Slightly drooping, head shaking	Drooping on one side	Drooping bilaterally, head tilt
Suckling reflex	Strong	Weak	Absent	
Eye discharge	No discharge	Small amount	Moderate	Intense
Nasal discharge	No discharge	Unilateral, small amount	Bilateral, cloudy or excessively mucous	Bilateral, abundant, mucopurulent
Cough	No cough	Isolated induced cough	Repeated induced cough, spontaneous cough	Repeated spontaneous cough
Respiration	Eupnea	-	-	Dyspnea
Fecal consistency	Normal	Semi-formed, pasty	Loose, remains on top of bedding	Watery, seeps into bedding
Skin elasticity	Returns to normal <2 seconds	2 seconds	2-4 seconds	>5 seconds
Eye depth (enophthalmos)	Normal	Slightly sunken (2-4 mm)	Sunken (4-6 mm)	Very sunken (> 6 mm)
Cleanliness	Clean thighs and body with little or no feces	Dirty tail head and hindquarters	Dirty tail head, hindquarters, and thighs/legs	Dirty tail head, hindquarters, thighs, and legs
Navel	Normal	Slightly swollen, no pain or warmth	Slightly swollen, painful, moist, or warm	Swollen, painful, warm, and foul odor
Joints	Normal	Slightly swollen, no pain or warmth	Swollen with some pain and limping	Swollen, painful, warm, limping
Rectal temperature (°C)	37.7 - 38.3	38.4 - 38.8	38.9 - 39.4	≥ 39.5

Adapted from McGuirk and Peek (2014); Renaud et al. (2018); Steerforth and Van Winden (2018); McCarthy et al. (2021).

Supplementary Figure 1. Number of calves with diarrhea during the experimental period, assessed by the fecal score.